

TEACHING SOME BUSINESS VOCABULARY

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Abstract. The article focuses on some traditional techniques for vocabulary teaching in the untraditional context of English for specific purposes – business English vocabulary teaching. Those techniques are based on the selection and presentation of collocations, synonyms, antonyms and paronyms, of words whose specialized meaning differs from their general English one, as well as of specialized words with some similarity in meaning, but also with a significant difference.

Keywords: English for specific purposes (ESP), business English, vocabulary teaching and acquisition.

INTRODUCTION

Teaching English for specific purposes (ESP) is directed towards learners' immediate professional and practical needs in accordance with their specialization. Its main goal is the development of specialized communicative competence in the respective field and its integration into learners' general professional competence, which is based on the correct use of the respective specialized vocabulary both in the foreign language and the mother tongue. Hence the necessity for a combination of some techniques for increasing the efficiency of its teaching and acquisition.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The object of this analysis is the economic vocabulary in business English teaching and the techniques for increasing the efficiency of its teaching and

acquisition. The main goal of the paper is to present a combination of techniques for increasing the efficiency of economic vocabulary teaching and acquisition. For the achievement of that goal, the following tasks are set: making a brief overview of the differences between teaching ESP and teaching general English; paying attention to students' insufficient specialized vocabulary knowledge at the beginning of their business English courses at university; justifying the need for a combination of different techniques for specialized vocabulary teaching, examining each and every one of them separately; outlining the role of term extractors.

The most suitable approach to teaching in the particular situation can be a combination of elements of different methods and/or personal decisions of the lecturer himself/herself in the particular environment of the particular workplace in accordance with the particular learners' needs (Dimitrova- Gyuzeleva 2015: 553). Hence the necessity for a combination of suitable approaches to teaching business English vocabulary in an academic context.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Lexical knowledge includes the acquisition of lexical units – words, expressions, collocations, phrases. The word as a fundamental lexical unit has a complex semantic and morphological structure. It comes into the structure of the sentence through the collocation, which reflects the lexico-semantic and grammatical links between words, realized by models typical of every single language. There is not a unanimous viewpoint in scientific literature about the level to which the collocation belongs because it combines categories of different levels – lexico-semantic, morphological and syntactic one.

Here are some examples of specialized collocations:

allocate resources/money – “to give a particular amount of resources/money to someone or something, so that it can be used in a particular way”

blow the whistle – “to bring something to the attention of other people in order to stop something bad from happening”

delegate responsibilities/responsibility – “to give a particular responsibility to someone else so that they do it for you”

fiddle the accounts/books/finances – “to dishonestly change a company’s accounts or financial records”

foot the bill – “to pay a bill”

go bankrupt – “to become unable to pay what you owe, and to have control of your financial matters given, by a court of law, to a person who sells your property to pay your debts”

pay money up front – “If you give someone an amount of money up front, you pay them before they do something for you.”

raise money/capital/funds – “to manage to get money to invest in a business, project, property, etc.”

run a business / a company – “to be in control of or manage a business / a company”

taking the minutes – “writing down what is said at a meeting and by whom”

To increase the efficiency of specialized collocations acquisition, lecturers of business English should select from coursebooks and the periodical press and present to students pairs or sets of specialized words which usually go together. Attention should be paid to their meanings and translation equivalents.

Selection and presentation of specialized synonyms

Here are some examples:

- **competitor or rival** (*noun*) – “a person, product, company, etc. that is trying to compete with others, for example, by trying to make bigger sales in a particular market; a person, company, product, etc. competing with others for

the same thing or in the same area”

- **cutting red tape** (*collocation*) or **reducing bureaucracy** – “reducing the number of official rules and processes that seem unnecessary and cause delays; reducing the quantity of complicated rules, processes, and written work that make it hard to get something done”
- **deceit** or **fraud** or **scam** (*noun*) – “dishonest or illegal methods used by a person or organization in order to get something or to make people believe that something is true when it is not; the crime of getting money by tricking or deceiving people, or a crime of this type; an illegal way of making money, usually by tricking people”
- **fringe benefits** or **perks** (*noun, plural*) – “extra things that are given to you by your employer in addition to your pay but are not in the form of money; advantages or extra things, such as money or goods, which you are given for doing your job”
- **labour union** or **trade union** (*noun*) – “an organization that represents the people who work in a particular industry, protects their rights, and discusses their pay and working conditions with their employers”
- **middleman** (*Pl* middlemen) or **intermediary** (*noun*) – “a person who communicates or makes arrangements between two people or groups who are unwilling or unable to meet or deal directly with each other; a person or organization that makes business or financial arrangements between companies or organizations that do not deal with each other directly”
- **nominal value** or **face value** or **par value** (*noun*) – “the value of a share, bond, etc. when it is made available for sale for the first time; the value or price that is shown on something such as stamps, coins, or paper money”.

CONCLUSION

In the paper, a brief overview of the differences between teaching ESP and teaching general English was made, attention was paid to students’ insufficient

specialized vocabulary knowledge at the beginning of their business English courses at university, the need for a combination of different techniques for specialized vocabulary teaching was justified, each and every one of them was examined separately, the role of term extractors was outlined. A combination of techniques for increasing the efficiency of economic vocabulary teaching and acquisition was presented.

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